

Cooperative RPL: Power-Smart Routing for Next-Gen IOT

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Abstract:

The deployment of numerous low-power, low-cost embedded devices is crucial for the advancement of the Internet of Things (IoT). Efficient routing protocols are essential to ensure seamless communication and optimize energy usage within these networks. The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) has standardized the IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low Power and Lossy Networks (RPL) to address these challenges.

In this study, we introduce Cooperative RPL (Co-RPL), an enhanced energy-efficient routing protocol that leverages node cooperation to minimize unnecessary packet transmissions and optimize power consumption. By implementing an Active/Sleep scheduling mechanism with a Round Robin approach, Co-RPL strategically selects active nodes for communication while placing others in sleep mode, thereby reducing energy expenditure and improving network efficiency.

Performance evaluations using the Cooja simulator in Contiki 3.0 reveal that Co-RPL significantly reduces network energy consumption compared to traditional RPL. Specifically, Co-RPL lowers the average radio listen ratio by up to 8% and the radio transmission ratio by up to 13%, leading to improved energy conservation. Additionally, it mitigates network congestion and enhances overall efficiency, making it a promising solution for energy-aware IoT networks.

Keywords: IoT, Contiki Cooja Simulator, RPL, Energy Efficient, Routing Protocol

1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of interconnected computing devices, embedded systems, and various entities such as people, animals, and objects. It enables seamless communication between these entities through a common platform, facilitating data exchange without the need for human intervention [17][19]. Since IoT relies heavily on remote sensing, low-power wireless sensor networks (LLNs) play a crucial role in its expansion. LLNs are characterized by constrained processing and storage capacities, particularly in low-power and lossy network (LLN) devices [16]. These limitations pose various challenges, especially in networking and communication, when deployed in harsh or resource-constrained environments.

LLNs rely on multiple resource-constrained embedded devices to relay data, making routing a critical aspect of their functionality. As specified by 6LoWPAN, the Routing Over Low-Power and Lossy Networks (ROLL) working group standardized RPL (IPv6 Routing Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks) as the primary routing protocol for LLNs [18]. RPL is considered a promising candidate for enabling machine-to-machine (M2M) and IoT

communication [20][21][23][26]. Designed as a proactive IPv6 distance-vector routing protocol, RPL addresses the challenges posed by large-scale networks with numerous nodes operating over unstable and lossy links.

Despite its effectiveness in meeting the requirements of low-power and lossy sensor networks, RPL still has areas that require further optimization. In particular, reducing packet exchange among nodes is critical for improving energy efficiency, network longevity, and Quality of Service (QoS).

In this paper, we propose Cooperative RPL (Co-Op RPL), an enhanced extension of RPL that introduces cooperative communication among network nodes. This approach minimizes the constant active participation of nodes in communication, thereby reducing energy consumption and improving network performance. Our method utilizes the potential communication range of the network to identify nodes for inclusion in the cooperative vector and determine their cooperative status.

Nodes within the cooperative vector can operate in either active or sleep mode at any given time. The Round Robin algorithm is employed to select an active node from the cooperative vector, while the remaining nodes enter a sleep state for a predefined duration τ . During this period, only the active node participates in communication, allowing Co-Op RPL to efficiently utilize network resources while significantly lowering energy consumption.

The primary contributions of this paper include the implementation of Cooperative RPL in the Cooja simulator within Contiki 3.0, along with a comparative performance evaluation of standard RPL and Cooperative RPL in terms of average energy consumption, radio duty cycle, and routing efficiency.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section II presents a literature review of recent research on RPL. Section III provides a comprehensive overview of RPL and the proposed Cooperative RPL. Section IV discusses the simulation results from Contiki OS and Cooja, comparing the performance of Cooperative RPL with standard RPL. Section V concludes the paper and outlines potential directions for future research.

2. RELATED WORK

Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) form the backbone of the Internet of Things (IoT) by enabling seamless connectivity between devices and the internet. However, these devices typically have limited memory and power resources, with storage capacities often restricted to around 100 kB. The performance of such networks is largely influenced by the operating systems used to manage them. Efficient routing in these networks has led to the development of the Routing Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks (RPL), which optimizes resource utilization.

RPL is a proactive distance-vector source routing protocol that operates on top of the MAC and physical layers of IEEE 802.15.4 networks [1]. Originally developed by Cisco Systems, RPL has been widely adopted for managing low-power, lossy networks in IoT environments.

Several studies have explored the implementation and performance of RPL using the Cooja simulator. One such study [1] implemented RPL in Cooja, conducting a comprehensive analysis of its performance. The findings suggest that RPL plays a crucial role in the advancement of IoT by efficiently utilizing available network resources. The simulation results demonstrated that the Minimum Rank with Hysteresis Objective Function (MRHOF) outperforms the Objective Function Zero (OF0) in terms of network efficiency and stability.

Another study [2] also integrated RPL into Cooja and analyzed its energy consumption under different network topologies. The results indicated that network topology alone does not significantly affect energy consumption in sensor nodes. However, when the transmission ratio (Tx/Rx) was modified to 50%, notable variations in energy usage were observed. The study attributed the low transmission ratio to poor link quality between nodes, often caused by external interference or environmental obstacles. The author concluded that poor transmission ratios negatively impact network performance, as sensor nodes require additional computations to determine optimal routing paths. This increased computational complexity results in higher energy consumption for each node.

A research study [10] analyzed the differences and similarities between the WSN simulator [11] and the Cooja simulator [12]. The study conducted two experiments to evaluate their performance. The first experiment assessed the ability of sensor nodes to extend network lifetime by enhancing mobile sink performance in Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs). The second experiment compared how effectively the two simulators replicated the behavior of WSNs. The findings indicated that WSN simulator could simulate mobility on the node sink, whereas Cooja supported the simulation of Powerline Communication Networks (PLC). The study concluded that WSN simulator was a more efficient simulator than Cooja.

Paper [13] contributed to the development of 6LoWPAN, the Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP), and ZigBee by investigating the operational efficiency of the stack protocol, modeled after the Internet Protocol (IP). Performance evaluations were based on end-to-end delay, throughput, and packet loss to determine the effectiveness of these protocols. The study found that 6LoWPAN successfully addressed the interoperability limitations of the ZigBee protocol, which previously restricted ZigBee to communicating only with sensor nodes using the same protocol. Additionally, RPL was identified as a suitable routing protocol for the spanning tree technique, where nodes formed a tree structure by identifying neighboring nodes. This process contributed to load balancing in RPL networks. The researchers proposed the Minimal Degree-RPL (MD-RPL) methodology, which incorporated routing metrics and node ranking to optimize network efficiency.

Another study [14] analyzed the operational efficiency of various RPL routing tree instances under low-power and lossy network conditions. Simulations were conducted to assess packet delivery ratio (PDR), latency, and tree convergence. The results demonstrated that using multiple RPL routing tree instances significantly improved network performance compared to a single RPL routing tree instance, particularly in terms of PDR, latency, and network convergence.

A study [15] evaluated RPL performance by restricting the transmission range of each node, considering that real-world conditions prevent ideal, unrestricted transmission. Performance metrics included packet delivery ratio (PDR), energy consumption, and transmission delay. These parameters were assessed using the Estimated Transmission Count (ETX) routing metric and two objective functions: Objective Function Zero (OF0) and Minimum Rank with Hysteresis Objective Function (MRHOF). The results provided insights into how transmission limitations and routing strategies impact RPL performance in resource-constrained networks.

3. Overview of Protocol

The Routing Protocol for Low-Power and Lossy Networks (RPL) utilizes optimized routes to transfer traffic from sensor nodes to a designated sink node [2]. RPL is a highly adaptive protocol that provides alternative routes when default paths become unavailable. It is particularly suited for networks with low power and high packet loss. One of the primary ways

RPL organizes network topology is through the creation of Destination Oriented Directed Acyclic Graphs (DODAGs).

A DAG (Directed Acyclic Graph) consists of a single destination where all network traffic converges. The DODAG structure includes a DODAG root, which has no outbound edges. The DODAG root is responsible for configuring various parameters, including Trickle timer settings, Path Control Size, Minimum Hop Rank Growth, and DODAG preference fields [2]. Each RPL instance operates with a unique Objective Function (OF), and multiple DODAGs can exist within a single instance.

Node rank is determined by its proximity to the sink node—closer nodes have higher ranks, while nodes farther from the sink experience lower ranks. The Objective Function (OF) is responsible for computing node ranks and defining route selection criteria. It dictates how nodes join a DODAG and how routing paths are optimized.

There are two primary types of Objective Functions (OF). Objective Function Zero (OF0) determines routing paths based on the hop count between source and destination. The Minimal Rank with Hysteresis Objective Function (MRHOF) utilizes the Estimated Transmission Count (ETX) metric, which considers link quality and the expected number of retransmissions needed for successful packet delivery.

RPL utilizes four key control messages for network operation. The DODAG Information Object (DIO) allows nodes to discover RPL instances and select DODAG parent nodes. The DODAG Information Solicitation (DIS) is used by nodes to request DIO messages, especially when an orphan node searches for a DODAG to join [2]. The Destination Advertisement Object (DAO) transmits destination information to the DODAG root. In non-storing mode, packets are forwarded recursively up to the root, while in storing mode, packets traverse through parent nodes until they reach an ancestor capable of delivering them to the destination. The DAO Acknowledgment (DAO-ACK) is a response message sent to acknowledge the receipt of a DAO message.

RPL employs a Trickle timer to control the frequency of control message transmissions, ensuring that updates are sent only when necessary to reduce network overhead. If a node detects consistent DIO updates from its neighbors, it increments its redundancy counter. If the number of consistent updates exceeds a predefined threshold, the node suppresses its own updates and doubles its listening period. If an inconsistency is detected, the timer resets, and the node broadcasts DIO messages more frequently to propagate updates across the network. When the network is stable, the Trickle timer reduces control message transmission to conserve energy.

The DODAG formation process begins at the root node (sink node), as shown in Figure 1. The root node initiates DIO message broadcasts to its neighboring nodes, which process and forward the messages to other nodes in the network. This process continues recursively, ensuring that all nodes become part of the DODAG structure.

If a node receives a DIO message and is not part of a DODAG, it calculates its path overhead based on the Objective Function (OF) of the sending node [10]. The node evaluates whether joining the DODAG is optimal and makes a decision accordingly. If a node receives a duplicate DIO message from the same DODAG, it discards the message. When a new node joins the DODAG, it calculates the best route to the root and assigns the sender of the DIO message as its parent in the DODAG hierarchy. The node then determines its rank and transmits a DAO message to inform the parent of its new position in the hierarchy.

Symbol	Description	Symbol	Description
N	Total of nodes in the Network	ζ	Current Consumption
n_i	Indicates ith node in the network	ψ	Co-operative Vector
n_j	Indicates jth node in the network	ξ	Average Energy Consumption
t	Time span	P	Data Packet
η	Power Consumption	R	Rank of a node
ϕ	Charge	τ	Co-Operative node Active time
i	Node chosen to be active amongst ψ	z	Node broadcasting dummy data packets

Table I: Used Notation Summary

Fig 1. Construction of DODAG in RPL

If an unknown node has not joined any DODAG system and has not received any DIO message from other nodes in the network, it periodically sends a DIS message to its directly connected neighbor. The DIS message requests DODAG information from the nodes directly connected to it. This process continues until the node receives a DIO message and successfully joins a DODAG system.

Overview of Proposed Algorithm Cooperative RPL:

While routing packets in an IoT network, instead of involving all nodes in communication, only a selected set of nodes actively participate. The primary objective is to reduce node participation, which helps conserve energy and extend the network's lifespan.

To achieve this, Cooperative RPL designates a set of nodes within the communication range of a packet as cooperative. Only one of these cooperative nodes is selected to be active at any given time, while the rest remain in sleep mode, minimizing energy consumption. These inactive nodes are not alerted to incoming packets but can still passively monitor other network communications.

Fig 2. Architecture of Cooperative RPL routing domain

Algorithm: Secure Cooperative RPL Packet Processing

1. Repeat:
 2. Broadcast authenticated dummy packets P with integrity checks (e.g., HMAC)
 3. Until condition $z \in \zeta$ is met
2. For each packet P :
 5. Verify Packet Authenticity:
 - o Check digital signature or message authentication code (MAC)
 - o Drop packet if verification fails
 6. For all nodes i in Communication Range of P and $i \in N$:
 7. Add node i to the cooperative set Ψ
 8. End For
3. For each node $j \in \Psi$:
 10. Set node i to Active Mode and all other nodes $(j-i)$ to Sleep Mode
 11. Set Cooperative Timer τ for i
4. Repeat Until Cooperative Timer Expires:
5. Process packet P
6. Check for Replay Attack:
 - o Validate timestamp or sequence number
 - o Drop packet if replay detected
7. If node i 's R_i is less than sender's Rank R_s :
8. Forward P
9. Update Routing Metrics η, ζ, ϕ, ξ
10. Else:
11. Discard P
12. End If
13. Check for Malicious Nodes:
 - o If a node forwards malformed packets repeatedly, blacklist it
 - o Maintain an anomaly detection log
14. End Repeat
15. End For
16. End For

Once a node is selected as active, its cooperative timer starts, and it begins accepting packets. Upon receiving a packet, the node checks whether it is encountering it for the first time. If so, it adds the packet's originator to its neighbor list and processes the packet only if its rank within the DODAG is lower than that of the originator. Otherwise, the packet is discarded.

After processing the packet, the active node updates its routing metrics, including transmission power, receiving power, and residual power, before forwarding the packet to its destination. The node then checks its cooperative timer to determine whether to continue as an active node or transition to sleep mode. The primary objective of Cooperative RPL is to optimize resource utilization in nodes, ultimately reducing energy consumption and extending the network's lifespan.

4. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section presents a report on the simulation results and analyzes them to assess the feasibility and effectiveness of the Cooperative RPL protocol for the Internet of Things (IoT) [8][9]. It outlines the simulation setup in the Cooja simulator, followed by a detailed performance comparison between the standard RPL protocol and the proposed Cooperative RPL protocol. The primary objective of the proposed protocol is to evaluate the impact of various factors on network performance and compare the results of Cooperative RPL with those of the conventional RPL specification.

A. Simulation Setup

The Cooperative RPL has been implemented on Contiki 3.0. Emulation serves as a practical approach for evaluating the performance of IoT protocols [3], which is particularly significant given the networking community's challenges in ensuring reproducibility. The actual Cooperative RPL code is deployed on emulated IoT devices using the built-in Cooja emulator, which is an integral part of Contiki 3.0.

B. Simulation results

In order to better grasp the functionality of Cooperative-RPL, we carried out extensive simulations in which we compared it to conventional RPL. We experimented simulation by altering the number of DAG nodes and the packet transmission rate; and observed what effect these changes had on network parameters like average power consumption, the average routing metric, and average radio duty cycle.

Fig 4. Average Routing Metric in Cooperative-RPL and in Conventional-RPL

Compared to Cooperative RPL, the average routing metric is higher in conventional RPL, as shown in Figures 4. A 30-minute simulation revealed a 36-packet reduction per node in the worst-case scenario (90 to 54). In traditional RPL, when two nodes (i and j) receive the same packet, both process and retransmit it independently, leading to unnecessary energy consumption. This redundancy reduces network energy efficiency. In contrast, Cooperative RPL leverages node collaboration, allowing only one node to remain active while the other enters sleep mode. This reduces packet transmissions by 50%, lowering network congestion and improving energy conservation. Consequently, the network experiences fewer packets and a lower average routing metric.

Fig 5. Average Power Consumption by nodes in Cooperative-RPL & Conventional RPL

Fig 5 shows the average power consumption by node both in Cooperative-RPL and conventional RPL. Through the usage of Powertrace's plugin, the Cooja simulator keeps track of how much energy is being consumed by the sensor node. Among the parameters that were measured were the energy used by radio listen, the energy used by radio transmit, the energy used by Low Power Mode (LPM), and the energy used by the central processing unit (CPU).

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed Cooperative RPL (Co-RPL) as an enhancement to the traditional RPL protocol. Co-RPL optimizes energy efficiency by incorporating the Active/Sleep concept alongside the Round Robin Algorithm. This approach selectively designates an active node from a cooperative set, allowing it to handle communication while other nodes enter sleep mode. As a result, unnecessary retransmissions are minimized, leading to significant energy savings.

Simulation results demonstrate that compared to conventional RPL, Co-RPL effectively reduces the average routing metric and lowers overall energy consumption. Specifically, Co-RPL reduces packet transmissions by up to 50%, mitigating network congestion and improving energy efficiency. Powertrace analysis within the Cooja simulator indicates that Co-RPL decreases average radio listen ratios by up to 8% and reduces average radio transmission ratios by up to 13%. These improvements directly contribute to enhanced network lifetime and performance.

For future work, we plan to investigate the impact of Co-RPL on low-power and lossy wireless sensor networks (WSNs) with mobile nodes, further exploring its potential in dynamic network environments.

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